

ESSENTIAL ALGORITHM OF INFORMATION BASES FOR FORMING INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MANAGERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8015048>

Abstract. *The article provides information on competence-oriented education and the problems of formation and development of information competence in future managers, as well as the importance of the types of information they use. On the basis of research and analytical data, an algorithm of fields and types of information related to the formation and development of information competence of future managers has been developed.*

Keywords: *competence, manager, global, information base, management, financial, marketing, personal, professional, psychological.*

Introduction

Modern civilized society requires specialists who can solve not only standard problems, but also non-standard problems of production and emergency situations quickly, creatively, think critically, and have the ability to self-develop and evaluate [1]. Of course, in the era of developing digital technologies, it is possible to ensure the future manager's information competence and develop it based on the principle of lifelong learning during professional activity only on the basis of distance education [2]. In the development of the model of formation and development of information competence of managers in the distance education environment, it is important to analyze the necessary information bases, create a classification, and research the processes of managers' adoption and assimilation of innovations.

Research methods

During the research, methods such as analysis of scientific and teaching-methodical literature, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment-test, mathematical-statistical analysis were used.

Results and discussion

Competence-oriented education was formed in the 70s of the last century in the USA and a number of Western European countries due to the fact that the requirements of the labor market do not match the educational results [3].

Problems of competence and issues of its formation Emelyanov Yu.N., Petrovskaya L.A., Kholodnaya M.A., Choshanov M.A., Yakovleva N.V. in scientific work, professional competence Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, Derkach A.A., Dobudko T.V., Zimnyaya I.A., Klimov E.A., Kuzmina N.V., Markova A.K., Shcherbakovlar A.I. and issues of expert's information competence Gofenberg A.V., Vitkovskaya N.G., Golubin D.V., Akulenko V.L., Zaitseva O.B., Tairova N.Yu. It has been thoroughly scientifically analyzed and improved in scientific works [4]. However, the problems of formation and development of information competence of future managers in the environment of distance education is a relatively unexplored area.

In many studies, the competence approach was viewed as the "genetic root" of complex, person-oriented, systematic activity, axiological, cultural and problem situational approaches in the field of pedagogy and psychology [5]. The interpretation of professional competence is different and fundamentally different from each other in terms of content. R. Hagerty, A. In Mayhew's research, professional competence is said to be the main part of the professional competence of any specialist [6, 7].

The competence of a manager is fundamentally different from that of other professionals. Because the manager, as a management staff, manages the human factor as well as the technological processes. This goes back to the issue of forming the psychological competence of future managers. Competence is a set of knowledge in a specific field that has a significant impact on the professional and life activities of a manager, is related to how well he performs his professional duties, is evaluated according to accepted standards, and develops through education (author's definition).

In this definition of competence, the main focus is on the set of knowledge, but it is worth noting that knowledge and competence alone are not the basis for evaluating a person as a competent specialist. Therefore, it is necessary to be able to competently apply the theoretical knowledge and practical skills acquired during the educational process in professional activities. In the definition, the use of the phrase "assessed by standards" implies the assessment of theoretical knowledge and practical skills or work performance of an expert on the basis of specific established criteria (standard, regulation, etc.). Therefore, the difference between this definition and other definitions makes it possible to select an employee or predict his future performance. In addition, the competence of the manager is evaluated by the ability to manage standard and non-standard tasks.

Before developing an improved model of information competence of future managers, we need to create an algorithm of information sources and types and areas of information necessary for a manager. Since distance education is directly based on Internet technologies, there are millions of information in the world Internet system, but one of the most important issues is to determine which information is necessary and important for future managers, i.e., the set of knowledge [8].

Based on research and analytical data, the algorithm of information fields and types related to the formation and development of information competence of future managers was developed by the author (Figure 1).

As mentioned above, the manager not only manages production processes, but he is also required to manage human capital and the team at the same time. In the set of knowledge related to the field of management, we can directly include the following characteristics that determine the organizational abilities of a manager:

- to have information about the main mutual relations in all internal and external environments of the organization;
- knowledge of organizational structures, formal and informal structures;
- information and knowledge about the internal structural structure of the organization, determination of goals and tasks, implementation of technological processes, effective management of human resources;

1.-Figure. Algorithm of fields and types of information related to formation and development of information competence of future managers Information about the field of management.

- to gain knowledge and skills on the methods of managing and organizing the spiritual environment in the organization, the forms and types of organization of work and cultural work on a scientific basis, and their use in decision-making.

Managers need to have and regularly update information in the field of rapid change management in the market economy and strong competition:

- regular provision of the development of the enterprise in conditions of strong competition, information on the ways of transition from one stage of development to another;
- information on quick and correct planning of changes, identification of the reasons preventing the introduction of innovations (new technology and technical tools, new management system, new forms of labor organization, etc.) and ways to eliminate them;
- It is required to have information about the methods of restructuring the organizational form of the company.

Information on the field of financial management. As a set of knowledge in this direction, we indicate the following:

- information on determining and evaluating financial results;
- information on proper budget planning and management;

- information on capital management, financial reporting;
- information on the formation of profit and ways to increase it, types of profit and product cost formation;
- it is necessary to have information about investments and their attraction

Must have knowledge of technical aspects of *project management*, including: planning, project management and ensuring timely implementation, risk management, quality management, new forms and samples of project documents, and evaluation of results. They are also required to search, download, and apply information related to project management principles and their effective use, as well as the development of the ability to see the project in accordance with the company's strategy, using distance learning resources.

Marketing information. Understanding that the enterprise's marketing strategy is a part of the overall strategy, the impact of the external (market relations, consumers, competition) and internal environment (profitability, profit, the issue of resource limitations and its composition, etc.) it is assumed that they will acquire new information regarding knowledge on marketing research and analysis of effectiveness of advertising companies.

It is necessary to develop oneself with new information related to the organization of customer-oriented activities, support of the demands and interests of external and internal customers or consumers, and the organization of quality service to customers even in difficult or conflicting conditions.

Information on personal professional and psychological knowledge. The information competence of the future manager is a person-oriented competence, and therefore personal characteristics play an important role in the formation and development of the specialist's information competence.

A set of information on the development of *strategic thinking* is the basis of the manager's activity. Understanding that the long-term strategy of the enterprise is developed on the basis of the principle of new, non-repetitive and advantage over internal competition, identification of the long-term goal, correct assessment of the potential of the enterprise to achieve the goal set in the development of the long-term strategy, development and implementation of the personnel planning program, control of results It is carried out through information about making and periodic evaluation.

Information on the formation of leadership skills. Since the manager is considered a management staff, it is required to regularly develop oneself with information related to the formation of leadership competence. Such types of information include labor relations in the team and relations with employees, establishing working relationships with other people, feeling social responsibility, solving problems efficiently and quickly, ensuring smooth development of production while supporting employees, moral environment in the team and includes a new body of knowledge about how to sustain a cohesive environment.

Information on the development of speech culture. Speech culture plays the most important role in the development of information competence of future managers. Speech culture is a social phenomenon that develops in close connection with the development of society, science and technology, cultural and literary life. As the cultural level of the members of the society increases, their speech becomes polished and polished, improving in accordance with the rules and norms of speech culture [9]. It is known from this definition that the manager must master the norms of oral and written literary language (pronunciation, accent, vocabulary, grammar, stylistic rules), as well

as have the ability to use the visual means of the language in accordance with the purpose and content of the speech in various communication-intervention situations. In the course of his professional activity, it is considered necessary for a manager of this type to get acquainted with new information on the development of speech culture through distance education.

A set of information on learning foreign languages. Knowledge of foreign languages is important for the manager in forming and increasing the export capacity of the enterprise, developing and improving production by attracting foreign investments.

Information on the formation of emotional intelligence. This feature determines the content of the reflexive component of information competence, that is: knows his abilities, opportunities, level of knowledge, fully understands his desires and tries to achieve this goal, can understand the emotional state of other people, can understand his emotions, actions and thoughts in a complex way. and can manage in problematic situations, a set of knowledge and tools for developing the ability to quickly recover from an affective state to its permanent state.

Information on the formation of communicative features. Able to see rapid changes in the conditions of the market economy and implement new strategies, make recommendations to senior management to implement new innovations, take advantage of business opportunities in the competitive environment, take the initiative in developing new concepts, new models based on international experience, and take responsibility. collects, a set of information on the development of abilities to create a moral environment suitable for the birth of new ideas in the team.

Information on special (technical) knowledge. As we mentioned above, the manager is required to have complete information about the technology of production processes and technical means of the enterprise, as he performs the duties of a manager or leader. Taking into account that nowadays technologies and technical systems are rapidly becoming obsolete, it is necessary for the manager to develop his knowledge about new technologies and new techniques during his professional activity through distance education.

Information on social, values and faith development. Any management staff, as well as managers, regardless of the form of ownership of the enterprise, should know, correctly understand and be able to implement the state policy in the social sphere. It is necessary to acquire complete knowledge and new information about faith in the country, one's profession, spiritual and educational values.

Legal and regulatory information. With the help of distance education or Internet technologies, the manager is required to familiarize himself with the new legal and regulatory documents related to his field during his professional activity. This information plays an important role in ensuring the rule of law in the management of the enterprise.

All types of information mentioned above should be focused on the goals and results of the company's strategic plan.

Conclusion

All types of information mentioned above should be focused on the goals and results of the strategic plan of the enterprise. The world experience shows that the widespread penetration of information and communication technologies and the Internet into the field of education opens a great way for the globalization of educational services. Due to the abundance of information in today's information space, it is very important for future managers to decide which information to use in their activities. Therefore, the classification of the information base developed in this study and the methods of its use are important in the formation of information competence of future

managers. In this classification, the information base (knowledge set) of future managers is considered to consist of management, management and marketing, as well as personal professional and psychological knowledge. It is best for future managers to follow this classification when building their information competence and developing it based on the principle of lifelong learning, otherwise they will get lost in unnecessary information in the global information space and lose a lot of time.

REFERENCES

1. Raximov O. D. et al. Modern educational technologies //Tashkent," Science and Technology" Publishing House. – 2013.
2. Rakhimov O. D. Innovative pedagogical technologies: the method of projects as a technology that improves the quality of education //Karshi, TUIT . - 2013. - T. 80.
3. Samoilova N.I. Pedagogical conditions of formation information competence of future engineers. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of candidate of pedagogical sciences. Kazan State Technological University. - 2007.
4. Temerbekova A.A. Formation of information competence of the teacher in the regional system of additional professional education. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. Moscow Pedagogical State University. -2009. URL:<https://www.dissercat.com/content/formirovanie-informatsionnoi-kompetentnosti-uchitelya-v-regionalnoi-sisteme-dopolnitelnogo-p>.
5. Karpechenko A.S. Formation of information competence of a modern manager. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of candidate of pedagogical sciences. Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Professional Education Kaluga State University. K. E. Tsiolkovsky. 2012Beknozaroza Z. Professional engineering students the problem of competence development and current status. //Society and innovation. -2021, №8. – P.56-606.
6. Davis E. Technognosis. - Ultra. culture, 2008 – P. 918.
7. Рахимов О. Электрон таълим ресурсларини яратиш талаблари ва технологияси. //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2016.№2. С. 45-50.
8. Speech culture. URL:<https://qomus.info/encyclopedia/cat-n/nutq-madaniyati-uz/>